

Determination of the Quantum Yield of Photoacids

By Edwin Amuga

Determination of the Quantum Yield of Photoacids

Introduction

Photochemical processes are governed by four photochemical laws that have evolved since the advent of photochemistry (Turro, 1991). The first law states that only the light absorbed by the system is effective in producing a photochemical change. This law means that the presence of light is not enough reason to cause photochemical activity. The molecule must absorb the right wavelength, which is somehow unique to the molecule, to affect a photochemical reaction or activity.

The second law states that each photon or quantum absorbed by a molecule has a certain probability of populating either the lowest excited singlet state S_1 , or the lowest triplet state T_1 . In the lowest excited singlet state, the electron jumps from a lower energy ground-state to the higher energy excited-state without changing its spin. In the triplet state, the electron of the molecule inverts its spin and occupies the lowest energy triplet state.

The third law states that each photon or quantum absorbed activates one molecule in the primary excitation step of a photochemical sequence. It relates to the first law of photochemistry, stating that light alone is not sufficient to cause photochemical activity. The substance must absorb the right wavelength to excite an electron from the low energy ground-state to the high energy excited-state.

For the last law of photochemistry, the lowest excited singlet and triplet states are the starting points (in solution) of most organic photochemical processes.

All photochemical process starts with the absorption of light that produces the excited-state which has properties that is very different than that of the ground state. Each excited-state species is very unique with its own energies, lifetime, and structure (Turro, 1991). Figure 1

shows a Jablonski diagram, devised by Aleksander Jablonski. In this diagram, the horizontal lines represent energy levels. The thick, black lines are the lowest energy state of that energy level.

For instance, a molecule absorbs a light of proper wavelength, causing its electron to be excited to the second excited singlet state, S_2 . The excited- state may then undergo three pathways to release the energy it gained through absorption of light. First are the radiationless processes represented in this diagram as wavy lines. Radiationless process converts one electronic state to another without involving the absorption or emission of radiation (Turro, 1991). The energy is released through heat caused by the collision of high-energy excited-state molecules with each other.

In Figure 1, the electron is excited to the fourth energy level of the second singlet state (S_2). It undergoes vibrational relaxation through collision, represented by the black wavy arrows. At the lowest energy level of S_2 , the molecule undergoes internal conversion. This is the intramolecular radiationless interconversion between different electronic states of like multiplicity like the singlet-singlet (S_1 to S_0) or triplet-triplet (T_2 to T_1). In this example, there is a singlet-singlet internal conversion from S_2 to S_1 .

At S_1 , it undergoes another loss of energy through radiationless processes until it arrives to the lowest energy level of the first singlet excited- state. At this level, the molecule may undergo the second pathway for energy release and that is through fluorescence.

Fluorescence is the phenomenon of emission from S_1 to the ground state S_0 (Turro, 1991). The inherent lifetime τ^0 , which is defined as the reciprocal of the rate constant for the disappearance of the excited-state, of this phenomenon is about 10^{-9} to 10^{-6} seconds.

If the excited-state at the lowest energy level of the first excited singlet state did not fluoresce, another pathway would be intersystem crossing which is defined as the intramolecular radiationless interconversion between singlet and triplet states (S_1 to T_1 ; or T_1 to S_0).

In the diagram below, the excited- state undergo intersystem crossing from the lowest energy of the first excited singlet state S_1 to the second energy level of the first excited triplet state T_1 . At the first excited triplet state, the molecule may then release energy through phosphorescence. It is the release of energy from the first excited triplet state T_1 to the ground state S_0 . It usually takes longer for phosphorescence to occur since transition from a triplet state to a singlet state involves a change in spin which is forbidden in quantum mechanics. Phosphorescence usually takes 10^{-3} to 3 seconds to occur for most commonly encountered organic molecules.

Figure 1. Jablonski Diagram explaining photochemical process.

The third photochemical process is the chemical involvement of the excited- state to produce or provide efficient chemical reactions. The excited-state may participate in reactions such as tautomerizations, isomerization, and photochemical reduction-oxidation reactions.

In this experiment, the photoisomerization of photo switchable molecules in solution will be investigated. In particular, photo switchable acids will be observed and how their behavior changes when different wavelengths of light are irradiated in them. Photoacids are a group of acids which changes its acidity upon the absorption of light (Johns *et. al*, 2014). Once these molecules absorb light, their acidity becomes more intense and the pH of the solution decreases. This happens because of photodissociations, or the release of protons upon the absorption of light (Johns *et. al*, 2014). There are usually two types of acids, the photoacid generators (PAGs) and the photoacids (PAHs). PAGs undergo an irreversible photodissociation whereas PAHs release proton through photodissociation and are usually thermally stable and reversible (Johns *et. al*, 2014). This experiment will focus on the family of photoacids called the benzothiazoles. The structure of which is shown below.

Figure 2. The structure of PA1, the photoacid that will be studied in this experiment.

Due to the presence of conjugation, this molecule is known to absorb light at 437 nm and with a molar extinction coefficient equivalent to $3.06 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Stranius and Borjesson, 2017). Photoacids are known to convert from being a weak acid to a strong acid upon absorption of light. However, this phenomenon is dependent on several factors and that includes the thermal

relaxation process upon switching the light source off. Aside from the absorption profile of these molecules, it is also important to note their photo isomerization quantum yield. This experiment will determine the experimental quantum yield of both the switchable isomers of PA1 and how it can be done through numerical methods.

Objectives

At the end of this study, the researcher must be able to:

1. Differentiate the absorbance of the photoisomers of the photoacid;
2. Measure the absorbance profile of the photoacid including its wavelengths of maximum absorption;
3. Determine the isosbestic point; and
4. Compute for the quantum yield of the photoisomers using a numerical equation.

Methodology

This study will involve the synthesis of the photoswitchable acid first. This can be done by combining a methyl benzothiazolium with an indazole aldehyde to form the benzothiazole shown below as PA1.

Scheme 1. The synthesis of the benzothiazole.

After synthesizing the benzothiazole, it can then be obtained to be studied for its photochemical activity. This molecule is known to highly soluble in DMSO and methanol

whereas it has a low solubility in water (Stranius and Borjesson, 2017). This study will utilize DMSO in measuring both the absorption peaks and the molar absorption coefficient.

Scheme 2. The photoreaction of PA1 to form PA1a and hydroiodic acid.

In order to determine the quantum yield of PA1 and PA1a with respect to different wavelengths of light, it is necessary to consider the kinetic parameters first. As in most cases of photoreversible reactions, the presence of light will convert PA1 to PA1a, following the equation,

In this chemical equation, the change in the concentration of PA1 to PA1a will be proportional to the photon flux (I) in s^{-1} , fraction of photons absorbed by PA1 (β), and the quantum yield of the photoisomerization from PA1 to PA1a (ϕ_{PA1}). The equation (1) for this would be as follows,

$$\frac{d[A]}{dt} \propto -\phi_A \cdot I \cdot \beta_A$$

As time progresses, PA1a will be converted back to PA1, considering that PA1a will absorb light at the irradiation wavelength which is 437 nm. Thus, equation 2 would be the reverse of equation 1 shown above.

$$\frac{d[A]}{dt} \propto \phi_B \cdot I \cdot \beta_B$$

Thus, the overall rate of the reaction needed in order to compute for the quantum yield is shown below as equation 3.

$$\frac{d[A]}{dt} = -\frac{\phi_A \cdot I \cdot \beta_A(t)}{N_A \cdot V} + \frac{\phi_B \cdot I \cdot \beta_B(t)}{N_A \cdot V} + k_{t,B \rightarrow A}[B]$$

The majority of detailed photoisomerization quantum yield estimations have been acted in a solution. To have the option to utilize equation 3 on a solution, the convergences of PA1 and PA1a should be homogenous inside the sample through constant stirring. This necessity must be kept with quick enough blending. The speed of stirring relies upon numerous variables, for example, the photon flux and size of light beam passing through the sample. Similarly, in ideal cases, no side reactions are happening in the photoisomerization reaction and PA1 is neatly changed over into PA1a. Overall, by using the Beer-Lambert's Law, the following equation would be used in order to determine the quantum yield of both PA1 and PA1a.

$$\frac{d[A]}{dt} = -\frac{\phi_A \cdot I \cdot \beta_A(t)}{N_A \cdot V} + \frac{\phi_B \cdot I \cdot \beta_B(t)}{N_A \cdot V}$$

The absorption of light in a photoisomerization reaction can be divided into two regimes, namely the total absorption regime and the low absorption regime. For the total absorption regime, it is assumed that all light passing through the solution is absorbed by PA1. This is the easiest to analyze regime because it can be considered that the absorption of PA1 is above 2 or at least 99% of the photons received by the solution is absorbed by PA1. At the same time, PA1a is assumed to not absorb any photons at all, making the calculations more manageable. When PA1a does not absorb any light at all or if the absorption is negligible, the equation is,

$$[A] \cdot \varepsilon_A \cdot 0.05 \geq [B] \cdot \varepsilon_B$$

Despite the simplicity of using Regime A, it has some drawbacks and disadvantages. One of those disadvantages is that it limits the number of concentration ranges that can be used in the experiment. Since this method will utilize absorption of light, the most viable method is UV-Vis

Spectrophotometry. Using UV-Vis will allow to determine if a species, like PA1a, can absorb light at higher concentrations. When this is the case, then regime 2 must be used.

On the other hand, Regime A also offers some advantages over Regime B. One of those advantages of using Regime A is the capability to simplify Equation 3 above when the thermal back reaction is slow compared to the photoisomerization. This simplified equation can then be used to analytically integrate the concentration of PA1 and the irradiation time to prove that there is a linear dependence between the two. In Regime A, the photochemical equation to determine the quantum yield can then be simplified to:

$$[A] = [A_0] - \frac{\phi_A \cdot I}{N_A \cdot V} \cdot t_{irr}$$

On the other hand, regime B requires that both the quantum yields for species PA1 and PA1a be determined. This results in a differential equation which cannot be solved through any analytical or mathematical simplification. The only way to solve this problem is by employing numerical methods to determine the quantum yields for both PA1 and PA1a. The starting equation for Regime B is shown as follows:

$$\beta_A(t) = \frac{[A] \cdot \varepsilon_A}{[A] \cdot \varepsilon_A + [B] \cdot \varepsilon_B} (1 - 10^{-Abs(t)})$$

In this equation, photons absorbed by PA1, represented as A, will be obtained by recording the absorbance at **the wavelength of maximum absorption**. In addition, Regime B also requires that the light passing through the sample is parallel or collimated, because nonparallel light or noncollimated light will result in a longer path length which can affect the accuracy of the data. One of the advantages of Regime B is that the quantum yields can be obtained even at

lower concentrations. It is also possible for Regime B to factor all thermal and photoinduced processes that are happening within the solution being observed.

There are also some disadvantages in using Regime B. One of those is that the molar absorptivity of PA1 must be different from the molar absorptivity of PA1a. This will become more complicated if both the molar absorptivity is unknown. This can be circumvented by determining the molar absorptivity of either of the solutions. For instance, the molar absorptivity of PA1 can be obtained first by recording the absorption spectrum of pure PA1, and then followed by irradiation of light of appropriate wavelength, and then plotting the absorption spectrum again. With Regime B, it is safe to assume that thermally stable products or intermediates are thermally stable and that only PA1 absorbs light at a specific wavelength. For this, the equation becomes,

$$\frac{d[A]}{dt} = -\frac{\phi_A \cdot I \cdot (1 - 10^{-Abs(t)})}{N_A \cdot V}$$

If both PA1 and PA1a absorb light at the irradiation wavelength (365 nm), then the above equation turns into this,

$$\frac{d[A]}{dt} = -\frac{\phi_A \cdot I \cdot \beta_A(t)}{N_A \cdot V} + \frac{\phi_B \cdot I \cdot \beta_B(t)}{N_A \cdot V}$$

In which the convergence of PA1 effectively can be resolved utilizing the Beer-Lambert law. Essential to note here is that the convergence of PA1 and the proportion of light consumed by PA1 both can be controlled by the absorbance esteem at the frequency of light. UV/Vis spectroscopy is consequently an advantageous strategy to perform photoisomerization quantum yield conclusions. From Equation above and onwards it is accepted that recorded absorbance esteems are taken at the frequency of illumination and that the way length of the light is the same

as the way length in the absorbance estimation. Besides, if warm cycles are moderate, just the genuine irradiation time should be taken into account.

Subsequently, the time among light and examination is of no outcome, which makes it conceivable to utilize separate test arrangements for illumination and examining. That is, Equation 13 can be utilized either to decide the photochemical quantum yield or then again to decide the photon motion utilizing a substance actinometer.

Shown below is the spectrum of both PA1 and PA1 a when light of different wavelengths was allowed to pass through. The black plot represents the absorption spectrum prior to irradiation of 437 nm light. The blue plot shows what happen when light of 470 nm is passed through while the pink plot shows after irradiation of 365 nm light.

Figure 3. The UV-Vis spectrum of PA1 after irradiating light with different wavelengths.

This shows that the photoacid can switch through the high acidity state PA1a without decomposing when light of 470 and 365 nm is allowed to pass through it. In addition, a DMSO solution of PA1 was prepared and results showed that it has a strong absorbance band at 437 nm as shown in the figure. From this, the molar absorption coefficient was calculated to be $3.06 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

After determining these quantities, a drop of triethylamine was added to the solution and irradiated at 470 nm. The calculated molar absorption coefficient of PA1a is $13369 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Afterwards, the solution was continuously irradiated at 365 for several minutes until the solution reached a photostationary state. During this state, the data and concentration was recorded and plotted. The results are shown below.

Figure 4. Plot of PA1a at several wavelengths.

As shown in this figure, there is a strong absorption at around 437 nm, which means there is a molecular species absorbing at this wavelength. This absorbance can be attributed to PA1 and the other wavelength was for PA1a. Also shown below is the data for the absorbance on different times and concentrations.

Figure 5. Plot of the absorbance against (a) wavelength and (b) time per minute.

This paper discussed the synthesis of a photoacid and determination of its quantum yield. Quantum yield is defined as the number of times a chemical event happened per photon absorbed by the molecular species. The calculations of quantum yields are important not just in this experiment but also on other occasions as well. It can include photodegradation processes, chain reactions, photocatalysis, and even photosensors (Turro, 1991).

Quantum Yield determination

Methodology

All the chemicals used in the experiment are commercially available and were therefore commercially acquired. The absorption criteria were recorded using Hitachi U-3010 spectrophotometer and the Hitachi F-700 fluorescence spectrophotometer used to record fluorescence emission spectra. The H-NMR was used to characterize chemical structures of the chemicals and the Hamamatsu Quantaurus spectrometer used to determine fluorescence quantum yields.

A solution of known concentration was prepared.

A drop of HCl was added to the solution to form an open ring

The sample was then subjected to UV spectrum with a molar absorption coefficient of $7053.2 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ at 365 nm.

A drop of triethylamine was then added to ensure the results form an open ring

The solution was then subjected to a radiation of 470nm. The 437 nm peak dropped and a new peak of 330nm with molar mass absorption coefficient of $753.5 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ at 365nm.

The nanoparticles were prepared through injection of μL THF of $10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ BPO into 10mL ddH₂O and stirred vigorously for 3 seconds at room temperature. The samples were then subjected to UV-vis absorption and fluorescence measurements.

The dry doped PMMA films were prepared by dissolving BPO/PMMA at a ratio of 1:100,w/w into dichloromethane. The solution obtained was applied on to commercial UV-LED set to obtain a covered film for light demonstration.

Results and Discussion

The N-[4-(benzothiazol-2-yl)phenyl]-octanamide BPO was synthesized by condensing aminobenzoic acid with aminobenzenethiol. It was then subjected to amidation using n-caprylic acid. The compound is soluble in common organic solvents including chloroform and hydroxyl but not in water as it has no hydroxyl group as the main reason for the difference in photophysical properties with similar compounds in the same family.

The absorption and emission spectrum of the BPO solution in THF and the aqueous suspension of their corresponding nano particles lie in the UV region implying that both dilute and nano particles of the compound are colorless. When subjected to excitation at the 365 nm light, the BPO solution in THF and the aqueous suspension of its nanoparticles show a range of emission properties. The emission maximum of the BPO n THF solution locates at UV region. The nano particle suspension of the compound shows a blue-violet emission with a maximum of 425 nm and a 0.124 fluorescence quantum yield owing to the enlarged π -electron conjugation in aggregates.

The Quantum yield calculation

$$Q_S = Q_R \times I_s/I_g \times A_g/A_s \times N_s^2/n_R^2$$

Q_S = quantum yield of the sample, Q_R = quantum yield of the reference, I_s =area under the PL curve of the sample, I_R =area under the PL curve of the reference, A_R = absorbance of the reference, A_S = absorbance of the sample, n_s =refractive index of the sample, n_R = refractive index of reference.

References

- Stranius, K. and Börjesson, K. Determining the Photoisomerization Quantum Yield of Photoswitchable Molecules in Solution and in the Solid State. *Sci. Rep.* 7, 41145
- Turro, N. J. (1991). *Modern molecular photochemistry*. Sausalito (california): university science books
- V. K. Johns, P. K. Patel, S. Hassett, P. Calvo-Marzal, Y. Qin and K. Y. Chumbimuni-Torres, *Visible Light Activated Ion Sensing Using a Photoacid Polymer for Calcium Detection*, *Anal. Chem.* 2014, 86, 6184–6187. (Published online: 3 June 2014).